

CAR ENGINE LUBRICATION SYSTEM MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR

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Abstract: Lubrication system of a car diesel engine, The main reasons for the indicated failures, Symptoms and causes of malfunctions of the lubrication system, Although there are not many failures of the lubrication system, Lubrication system repair.

Key words: malfunctions in the lubrication system, their causes, diagnosis of the lubrication system, maintenance of the system, repair of the lubrication system.

Lubrication system of a car diesel engine (Fig. 1). Basically, it turns "dry" rubbing into "wet" rubbing and cools the parts. A modern system performs several functions:

- reduces the force of mutual friction between details;
- cools the details;
- washes out the corrosion products of the detail and particles of dirt from between the slits;
- protects surfaces from corrosion;
- implements the control function (hydraulic compensator adjusting the heat gap of the valves, hydraulic tensioner of the GTM drive) [1].

Although there are not many failures of the lubrication system, they cause serious consequences. The disadvantages of this system are as follows:

- damage to the oil pump and eating of details;

- damage to the oil pump seal;
- filling of the oil filter;
- loosening of the oil filter from its hardened place;
- failure of the oil pressure sensor;
- failure of the reduction valve;
- decrease in oil level.

Figure 1. The structure of the lubrication system:

*1-oil pump, 2-oil drain cover, 3-oil receiver, 4-reservoir valve, 5-oil channel,
6-plug, 7-oil sensor, 8-oil stove tap, 9-oil stove, 10-oil filter.*

The main reasons for the indicated failures:

- violation of operating rules (use of low-quality oil, non-observance of oil and filter replacement period);
- low-quality maintenance and repair of the lubrication system;
- excessive use of system elements.

Symptoms of a malfunction of the lubrication system include:

- low oil pressure;
- increase in oil consumption

The decrease in oil pressure is indicated by the lighting of the warning lamp on the instrument panel. When the oil pressure is reduced, the operation of the car is prohibited [2-3].

An increase in oil consumption is determined by the dipstick of the engine. In some cars, it is also possible to determine the oil level electronically (the control lamp is installed on the instrument panel).

External symptoms of lubrication system failures and their causes are listed in the table below (Table 1) [4].

Table 1

Symptoms and causes of malfunctions of the lubrication system

System failure symptoms	Causes of system failures
Lower oil pressure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- failure of the oil pump and corrosion of its parts;- clogging of the oil filter;- failure of the oil pressure sensor;- hardening of the reduction valve;- low oil level
Excessive oil consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- failure of the crank mechanism;- failure of the gas distribution mechanism;- clogging of the crankcase ventilation system

Lubrication system maintenance includes:

- control the density of compounds;
- checking the oil level in the crankcase;
- constant monitoring of the temperature in the engine and lubrication system (especially when the engine is hot and under load);
- cleaning and washing the centrifugal oil filter and crankcase ventilation system;
- replacement of oil and oil filters in the system.

Before starting the engine, it is necessary to check the density of the lubrication system and the oil level in the crankcase using a dipstick. If possible, it is necessary to turn the crankshaft several times in order to lubricate the working

surfaces after the engine has not been fired for a long time. This reduces the eating of details [5].

The viscosity of cold oil is relatively high, so after the engine starts, it is slightly heated to ensure that the oil reaches all the details. In a heated engine, the oil temperature should be 70...90 °C and the pressure should be 0.15...0.35 MPa. Low pressure means that the oil level is below the norm, it is leaking out, and the gap in the connecting rod and main bearings exceeds the norm.

It is determined by hearing that the centrifugal oil filter is working. after the engine is turned off, the sound of the rotor should be heard for 0.5...1 minute. The rotor and the inner part of the filter are cleaned and washed after 120...240 hours of engine operation, depending on the operating conditions [6].

Engine oil is changed after the interval recommended by the car manufacturer in the following sequence:

- after stopping the engine, hot oil is quickly drained;
- the coarse filter is cleaned and washed, the fine filter is replaced with a new one;
- the crankcase is replaced with clean oil;
- the density of the lubrication system is checked with the engine running.

The following tasks are performed during maintenance of the lubrication system:

- external control of system devices and conductors;
- control of oil level and quality in the crankcase;
- oil replacement;
- check the oil pressure and temperature in the running engine.

The oil level in the crankcase is checked before starting the engine, periodically during operation and after work.

It is recommended that the oil temperature not be lower than +40°C before starting the car.

A decrease in oil pressure occurs as a result of corrosion of the core and connecting rod necks and bearings, as well as the failure of the reduction valve. If the oil pressure in a diesel engine shows "0", it is necessary to immediately stop the engine and determine its cause. Such a situation occurs when the oil transmission tract is broken, the valve of the pump is clogged, and the oil pump fails [7].

It is recommended to change the engine oil in GM-Uzbekistan cars operating in the territory of our republic according to the factory instructions and after the specified period depending on the operating conditions. According to the factory instructions, it is recommended to use SAE 5W/30, SAE 10W/30, SAE 10W/40 and SAE 15W/40 class motor oils in GM-Uzbekistan cars. Only their selection is made according to the external temperature (Fig. 2) [8].

Figure 2. Chart for selecting motor oils based on outside temperature.

One of the most important factors in ensuring the uninterrupted operation of the engine is the replacement of engine oil at regular intervals. But many people make simple mistakes during the oil change process (Figure 3), and this mistake leads to engine failure.

Figure 3. Oil injection process

It is known to everyone that the technical service period of modern cars is 10...20 thousand km, but periodicity is recommended according to the regulations when cars are operated under ideal conditions [9].

Getting stuck in traffic jams in urban conditions and driving at high loads destroys the lubricating and protective properties of motor oils, so it is advisable to change the oil not at 10...20 thousand km, but at 8...15 thousand km.

When changing the oil, its level is less than the norm (below the "Minimum" mark on the dipstick (Fig. 4)) causes the engine to not work smoothly. Due to the lack of oil, the parts of the gas distribution mechanism, piston rings and other moving parts wear out faster. As a result, the piston can even get stuck in the cylinder of the engine.

Figure 4. Checking the oil level in the crankcase

Too much engine oil can cause many problems. An increase in oil pressure leads to the failure of seals and plugs (leaking oil) and excessive oil consumption, spark plug oiling and soothing of parts, and oil pump overload.

The main thing is to remember that semi-synthetic oil should be used in mineral oil, and only synthetic oil should be used in semi-synthetic oil. It should be remembered that it is absolutely impossible to do this the other way around, you should not mix transmission oil and mix engine oils in diesel and gasoline. Such combinations, in turn, can lead to unfortunate situations for the engine [10].

Lubrication system repair. Repairs to the system include replacing the water pump and centrifugal filter for worn, broken and damaged parts.

During the operation of the engine, the surface of the oil pump cover, gear, drive shaft and bushing are eaten. The cover surface is restored by grinding. In this case, the gap between the surface of the cover and the side of the gear should be 0.2... 0.3 mm. The gap is checked by the shift of the drive shaft along the axis with the help of an indicator.

The drive shaft is restored to standard size by chroming or by routing to the next repair size. The eaten chestnut is replaced with a new one. After repair, the pump is tested using a special device (Fig. 5). During the test period, the pressure generated by the pump at 400 min^{-1} should be 0.05 MPa and 0.25 MPa at 400 min^{-1} . Otherwise, the pump is unusable [1-3].

Figure 5. Oil pump tester form.

1-electric engine; 2nd oil pump; 3-manometer; 4th oil channel; 5-keyed hole triplet.

During engine repair, the filter is washed, the filter element and defective parts are replaced with new ones.

Plate-shaped filter elements are placed on the coarse filters of most engines (Fig. 6).

To disassemble the filter, the dirty oil is poured from the strainer, the cover bolts are loosened and it is removed together with the seal and the filter elements and the transfer valve. The details of the housing, filter element and transfer valve are washed in kerosene, then sprayed with compressed air.

Figure 6. Oil cleaning coarse filter:

1 drain plug; 2nd silencer; 3-sturgeon with cleaning plate; 4-transfer valve; 5-transfer valve spring; 6-rotary filter element holder; 7-filter plate; 8th star; 9-cleaning plate.

The filter element is placed in a paraffin bath without dividing it into pieces, and is washed by turning the holder.

A fine filter with a cardboard filter element is replaced with a new one, and the inside of its case is washed with kerosene. In order to properly seal the lid and the body, it is necessary to mark the places of their connection and put them in their place during assembly [11].

After washing, inspecting and collecting the filters, they are tested in a special device under a pressure of 0.6 MPa, under such pressure, oil should not flow from the filters.

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